

MORAL VALUES IN THE WORKS OF ABU NASR AL-FARABI

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Abstract. *The article raises questions of human morality and character—etiquette as the most important issue in the spiritual culture of the Renaissance. This is because the trait that distinguishes humans from their environment and other living beings, along with reason, is their morality. Therefore, reflection on morality consists of the study of man, humanity, and anthropology. That is why ethics occupies one of the leading places in this period. Thinkers and poets of the Renaissance paid great attention to morality, ethics, and its manifestations in various spheres of life in their works. During this period, morality and reason were inextricably linked. Wise morality was interpreted as morality based on thinking, and the doctrine of morality as habit, practical morality, emerged. We saw that this doctrine first appeared in the works of Al-Farabi.*

Al-Farabi considered questions of morality and ethics in their inseparable connection with the intellectual qualities of man — “mind” and “wisdom.” Therefore, the moral concepts and categories he identified and analyzed are interpreted not only as expressions of behavioral norms existing in human relations, but also as the results of people's intellectual activity throughout their history. Al-Farabi pays great attention to education and upbringing in the formation of personality. Education is the provision of scientific and theoretical knowledge to young people through reading and study. Upbringing is teaching young people the moral norms and practical skills necessary for them to master a certain craft. Al-Farabi, in his work “On the Attainment of Happiness,” shows that education should be based on a movement from the simple to the complex. Al-Farabi understands high moral qualities to be such as knowledge manifested in actions, wisdom, prudence, conscientiousness, humility, setting the goals of the majority above one's own goals, the pursuit of truth, love, spiritual perfection, and love of justice, and negative moral qualities to be ignorance, cunning, lies, injustice, cruelty, greed, avarice, and wealth. The pursuit condemns indulgence in various passions.

Keywords: *character, etiquette, society, youth, scientist, nation, happiness, science, education.*

INTRODUCTION

Society is a collection of people of different ages, characters, professions, and nationalities. It is defined by the relationships between different people in public life, their participation in solving political and economic problems, the creation of material and spiritual goods, their behavior at home, on the street, in places of recreation, at work, and in educational institutions, their mental states, and their culture of interaction.

A person is born and raised in a family, formed as a personality in society, but much depends on the person themselves. Self-education is a person's struggle to achieve physical and spiritual perfection. Self-awareness is the ability to understand how a person, as a member of society, interacts with the environment and people through their strengths, thoughts, feelings, and actions, and to analyze their actions and relationships with others.

If the family environment is organized on the basis of morality, etiquette, and cultural norms, if conditions are created for the proper formation of young people in life, then the children in the family will develop properly. A distinctive feature of raising a child in an Uzbek family is that, first and foremost, the child is raised in a spirit of respect for adults. In this case, the child is taught to respect adults without suppressing their desires, initiative, will, and courage. Nowadays, it is generally accepted that interest is an individual psychological characteristic of a person. However, some sources also define interest as a motive that helps to achieve the right goal in a certain area, to get acquainted with new factors, and to fully and deeply reflect reality. Accordingly, there are opinions that interest is a process of discovery, a process of cognition, which is characterized by positive emotions and manifests itself in a person's desire to learn more about an object, obtain more information about it, and understand its essence.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In the works of such great Renaissance thinkers as Razi, Kindi, Al-Farabi, Ibn Sina, Beruni, Battoni, Tusi, Nizami, and Navoi, Greek scholars such as Hippocrates, Galen, Pythagoras, Euclid, and philosophers such as Socrates, Plato, and Aristotle are mentioned with great respect as masters of science and education, fighters for the triumph of reason and knowledge.

Socrates was an ancient Greek philosopher known in the Middle East as Socrates. He paid particular attention to the human mind, intellectual exercises, the art of discussion and debate, education and the improvement of thinking, as well as ethics based on the activity of the mind. Socrates paid great attention to ethics, especially practical ethics. In his opinion, no one is evil by choice, but evil is the result of ignorance and misunderstanding.

The most influential thinker in the Middle East was the ancient Greek philosopher and encyclopedist Aristotle, who is known in the East as the “first teacher,” Aristotle, and Arastu.

Aristotle's major works, such as *Metaphysics*, *On the Heavens*, *Ethics*, *On the Parts of Man*, *Rhetoric*, and *Topics*, describe the knowledge that is necessary for a person in life.

Nasir Khisrav developed Ibn Sina's teachings in his philosophical views, based on them, paid great attention to socio-political issues, and fought for free thought. He is “*Jami ul Hikma*”. He is the author of such philosophical epics as “*Wajh Din*,” “*Devon*,” and “*Saodatnoma*.” Hisrav was one of the encyclopedic minds of his time, and in his worldview, he thought about the role of worldly reason, that it is the most perfect achievement of human nature. In matters of morality, Hisrav defended the character and customs of working people and praised the highest moral virtues.

Abu Rayhan Beruni says in his works that when raising a child in a family, special attention should be paid to maintaining moderation in his behavior, and this can be achieved by protecting the child from the fear of strong anger, sadness, and insomnia. One must always be ready to find what is desirable and useful for children and keep away from their eyes what they do not like. This has two advantages. On the one hand, it benefits the child's soul, because bad behavior is the result of various behavioral disorders. Also, if bad behavior becomes a habit, it can lead to behavioral disorders. As Beruni emphasizes, poor upbringing in the family can not only affect the family itself, but also have a negative impact on other families and the society around it. Therefore, proper upbringing is an important foundation for family happiness.

METHODS AND RESULTS

Abu Nasr Muhammad ibn Muhammad ibn Ozluq ibn Tarkhan al-Farabi was a great scholar of the Renaissance in Central Asia and throughout the East, a thinker who reflected in his works

the main elements of the advanced philosophical thought of his time, and one of those who expressed broad ideas about the highest moral virtues of man in his works.

Al-Farabi was a great philosopher, linguist, logician, mathematician, psychologist, and lawyer. He was a scholar who was well acquainted with Greek culture, science, and philosophy, and who devoted his remarkable talent throughout his life to the development of medical sciences, advanced philosophy, and socio-political thought.

Al-Farabi successfully mastered mainly theoretical sciences — mathematics, logic, theoretical medicine, music theory, natural science, the basics of law, philology, and other sciences. Literature states that before pursuing science, Al-Farabi was a judge, but then devoted himself to the search for truth and secular sciences—reading—and left his judicial career.

In the Middle Ages and in the works of the Renaissance, attention was paid to the question of reason. The encyclopedic minds of the Renaissance — Abu Nasr al-Farabi and Abu Ali ibn Sina — also paid great attention to the question of reason in their works.

In his work *Ihsa al-Ulum*, Al-Farabi studies the conscious actions of people, their character—habits, natural needs, skills, activities formed from them, levels of life, and methods. According to Al-Farabi's teachings, the material world existed before humans and their senses and minds; humans and their minds are the highest product of the development of the material world, and humans differ from animals in their organs, their ability to understand nature, their minds, and their language. Man begins to know the material world through his senses and from there rises to intellectual knowledge, to thinking. The moral character of man, the achievement of spiritual perfection, is not determined by anyone, but is in the hands of man himself.

In his treatise “On the Mind,” Al-Farabi expresses the following views on the mind:

We call a person intelligent if they possess a sharp mind and understanding, as well as virtue. Such a person must direct all their abilities and understanding toward doing good deeds, as well as toward abstinence and refraining from evil deeds. Only such a person can be called intelligent and have a correct mind.

Intelligent people are those who are virtuous, sharp in their reasoning, devoted to good and useful deeds, have a great talent for discovering and inventing necessary things, and refrain from evil deeds. In raising young people to be physically strong and well-rounded, Al-Farabi analyzes intelligence in two aspects: from the point of view of intellectual power, which exists as a natural characteristic of every person, and from the point of view of the general development and advancement of intellectual knowledge, which is characteristic of humanity as a whole.

He interprets intelligence as an integral characteristic of a person. Al-Farabi first of all divides it into two: theoretical and practical intelligence. With the help of theoretical intelligence, a person acquires knowledge. It shows a person's ability to master general, abstract, theoretical knowledge. However, theoretical intelligence does not directly answer the question of whether a person has mastered science or not. Practical intelligence depends on the path of acquiring knowledge, desires, abilities, and interests.

Since intellectual activity stems from human nature, from its essence, Al-Farabi also derived moral norms from everyday human activity. Moral norms arise from specific relationships between people in life. They change and develop.

Moral qualities and virtues, scientific knowledge, skills, and various arts are acquired by a person in the course of their personal life, under the influence of the external environment. Al-Farabi says in his works that will plays a big role in this. The social environment, relationships in society, and will are crucial in shaping a person's moral and spiritual character.

The pursuit of science requires a high level of skill. For example, to be a true scientist, a person must be well-rounded, that is, intelligent and interested in achieving intellectual purity. “A person who wants to study science,” he says, “must be young and modest, healthy, well-mannered and educated, firm, free from deception and fraud, able to protect themselves from various negative actions, and respect scientists.”

There are many books and recommendations on raising young people to be physically strong and well-rounded. However, there are very few books and recommendations that help young people achieve spiritual, mental, and moral maturity. That is why there are major shortcomings and a lack of culture in the relationships between our young people. Al-Farabi, in his work “What Should Be Learned Before Philosophy,” expresses the following thoughts on etiquette and morality:

In his opinion, “only a person who combines twelve innate qualities is a moral person”:

1. All the organs of such a person must be so perfectly developed that he can easily do whatever he wants with them.

2. He must be able to quickly and correctly understand all questions, discussions, and opinions, understand their meaning, be able to quickly notice the speaker's goal and the truthfulness of the opinion expressed.

3. Let his memory be very strong, and let him never forget anything he has seen, heard, or loved.

4. Let your mind be so quick and sharp that as soon as you sense a sign of something, you quickly understand what that sign means.

5. His speech should be clear, and he should be able to express his thoughts and comments fluently and clearly.

6. May he have a love of knowledge and reading, and may he be able to easily absorb the knowledge he wants to acquire without feeling tired.

7. Do not be greedy in eating and drinking.

8. Let him love the truth and those who stand for the truth, and let him despise lies and liars.

9. Let his spirit be proud and honor his conscience, and let his spirit by nature strive for higher and nobler things than base ones.

10. Let him look with disgust upon wealth and the pleasures of life.

11. Let him be one who, by nature, loves justice and those who fight for justice, and who hates injustice and oppression. Let him be fair to his people and others. Let him promote justice among people, giving everyone what he considers beautiful and good, and eliminating and preventing the consequences of injustice.

12. Let him be just, but not stubborn; let him not be stubborn in the face of justice; let him not succumb to arrogance, but let him be firm in the face of any humiliation; let him be firm in doing what he considers necessary; and let him be fearless, courageous, and know no fear or weakness.

CONCLUSION

According to the Law on Education, one of the main goals of secondary education is to develop young people's ability to think and analyze independently. It is no coincidence that this goal is enshrined in the law on general education. Young people who have developed the skills of independent thinking and analysis can consciously determine their future and successfully accomplish the tasks set before them in their future lives. Moral values should be of great

importance in order for young people to achieve their goals, be interested in learning, pursue their favorite profession, and study in areas that a person will study throughout their life.

People's interests differ from each other in scope. There is also a category of people whose interests are focused on only one area. People in the other category have interests in a number of areas, disciplines, and subjects. However, one interest in different areas cannot negatively affect another if they have the ability to manage them rationally. Narrow interests can often be seen as a negative phenomenon, but at the same time, their breadth can also be analyzed as a disadvantage. However, for a person to develop into a well-rounded personality, it is necessary that the scope of their interests be broad rather than narrow.

That is why the encyclopedic mind of the Renaissance, Abu Nasr Farabi, explained in detail in his works the highest moral qualities, intellect and its types, will, and interests.

For the development and stabilization of a person's interests, it is necessary to provide them with a solid foundation for engaging in activities that form the basis of those interests, to engage in them purposefully, and to awaken inclinations in them so that interests can become motives, needs, and convictions.

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